

ON THE STUDY OF LEAD-ACETATO COMPLEX ION

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Various hypotheses regarding the nature of the compound formed when a lead salt is treated with an alkali acetate has been critically examined. From thermometric and conductometric measurements it has been definitely shown that the main reaction results in the formation of a cationic complex, $(\text{Pb-C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2)^+$ and by utilising Job's method of continued variation, the dissociation constant of this complex cation has been determined.

The observation that lead sulphate dissolves in ammonium acetate is of classic application in analytical chemistry. Similar behaviour of other sparingly soluble lead salts towards alkali acetates has been the subject matter of frequent discussion for the last forty years and various hypotheses regarding the nature of the reaction has been proposed from time to time, but unfortunately the conditions under which the experimental data have all been obtained are not free from objections and so the conclusion arrived at cannot be fully relied upon.

The object of the present investigation is to examine the various hypotheses and to study the reaction from different physicochemical standpoint. Thermometric (Dutoit, *J. chim. phys.*, 1921, 19, 324) and conductometric measurements have been utilised as guiding indicators to ascertain at what proportion the reaction actually takes place and by utilising Job's principle of continued variation (*Job, Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928) the nature of the complex and its extent of dissociation have been ascertained.

The fact that lead acetate is a poor conductor of electricity led Noyes and Whitcomb (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 747) to suppose that the solubility of lead sulphate in ammonium acetate was due to the formation of undissociated lead acetate by metathesis. From a preparative point of view White (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1904, 31, 4) postulated that solubility of sparingly soluble lead salts in alkali acetates was due to the formation of a complex aceto-plumbite anion. Sanved (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1967) in a review of the nature of the complex formed, referred to the work of Blomberg (*Chem. Weekblad*, 1914, II, 1030) and that of Canrad (*Diss. Göttingen*, 1903) on the complex nature of lead acetate itself and summing up all the evidences known till then he put forward the hypothesis that the ion formed is probably $[\text{Pb.C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2]^+$, a result of primary dissociation of lead acetate. Edmonds and Birnbaum (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2367) very recently from a study of the solubility of lead iodate in ammonium acetate at constant ionic strength in the presence of varying acetate ion concentration, have supported the conclusion of Sanved and determined the value of the dissociation constant of complex cation $[\text{PbC}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2]^+$.

In discussing the various theories stated above our observation needs first be mentioned. We started with lead nitrate and ammonium acetate and by thermometric and conductometric measurements at various concentrations have arrived at the definite conclusion that the reaction always takes place in the molecular proportion of 1 : 1, i.e., one molecule of lead nitrate reacts with one molecule of ammonium acetate.

As regards the theory of metathesis due to Noyes and Whitcomb (*loc. cit.*), first objection has been raised by White by pointing out the fact that lead acetate solution is a good solvent for lead chloride where question of metathesis does not arise. Low conductivity of lead acetate has been explained by Blomberg as due to the complex nature of lead acetate itself and not due to its undissociated character. Finally the formation of lead acetate in such a reaction requires that the reaction should take place in a proportion where $\text{Pb} : \text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2$ is 1 : 2, whereas we have definitely showed that the only reaction that always takes place is in a molecular ratio 1:1. From the facts stated above Noyes and Whitcomb's theory of metathesis in such cases can be discarded altogether.

The hypothesis of White (*loc. cit.*) as to the formation of a complex aceto-plumbite anion also requires that the reaction must take place in a molecular proportion where $\text{Pb} : \text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2$ is 1 : 2, which is against experimental evidence. The solid compounds that White isolated may not have any appreciable existence in solution.

As regards the third hypothesis due to Sanved (*loc. cit.*) that the solubility of sparingly soluble lead salts in alkali acetates, as to the formation of a cationic complex, has got its support from the work of recent investigators (Edmonds and Birnbaum, *loc. cit.*) already mentioned and also from our own results too. But the work of the above investigators is not free from objection.

In their study of the solubility of lead iodate in varying concentrations of ammonium acetate solution by keeping the ionic strength constant and unimolecular by introducing ammonium perchlorate solution of proper strength, the authors have courted the probability of formation of a series of lead acetato-perchlorates which have been shown to exist in various forms of complex aggregation by Weinland and Stroch, (*Ber.*, 1922, 55B, 2706). The following lead acetato-perchlorates have been described. The measurements of their conductivities and the comparison of these values with those of binary, tertiary and quaternary electrolytes led Weinland and his school to represent them as follows :—

The salts are without exception crystalline and (3) can be crystallised from aqueous solution. Besides these compounds, basic lead-acetato-perchlorates and acetato-perchlorates containing lead in anion (Weinland, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1921 34, 354) have also been described. The following among them are so stable that these can be crystallised from warm water without any decomposition.

Secondly the solubility of lead iodate in molar ammonium perchlorate (Edmonds and Birnbaum, *loc. cit.*) is about five times its solubility in water and this also forecasts some complex formation which may affect the nature of the reaction and equilibrium constant too.

The third factor which is of importance in the application of solubility in such cases is the effect of the common ion. The common ion may have a two-fold effect. In this case if the reaction takes place as follows :

the liberated IO_3^- will depress the solubility of lead iodate and further concentration of IO_3^- ion may form complex ions like $\text{Pb}(\text{IO}_3)_3^-$; $\text{Pb}(\text{IO}_3)_4^{2-}$ thereby increasing the solubility of $\text{Pb}(\text{IO}_3)_2$.

FIG. 1

Thermometric titration curves

Curves I & II represent respectively, 25 c.c. of $M/2\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + 2M\text{-Am. Ac.}$, and 40 c.c. of $M/4\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ with $M\text{-Am. Ac.}$

FIG 2

Conductometric curve

Curve III—75 c.c. of $M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ with $2M\text{-Am. Ac.}$

From all the facts stated above question naturally arises that either the solubility curve of Edmonds and Birnbaum (*loc. cit.*) represents a resultant of the opposite effects and does not represent the true state of affairs or the prominent reactions have taken place in a molecular ratio of 1 : 1 by the formation of acetato-iodate and acetato-perchlorate of Pb and the other ions, either complex or simple, have no appreciable influence

in determining the nature of the curve but may exercise certain influence on the value of the dissociation constant.

Considering all these facts it becomes quite clear that the study of such a complex system in a heterogeneous equilibrium like this may lead to unavoidable errors of serious consequence: on the other hand by following Job's principle of continued variation (*loc. cit.*) in a homogeneous system, a better information and a more correct solution can be arrived at.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—Merck's lead nitrate of reagent quality was recrystallised twice from dilute nitric acid solution. Merck's ammonium acetate of the reagent quality was also used in all measurements.

FIG. 3

Conductometric curve

Curves IV—VI represent respectively $M/10\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/10\text{-Am. Ac.}$, $M/20\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/20\text{-Am. Ac.}$ and $M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/30\text{-Am. Ac.}$

FIG. 4

Conductometric curve

Curves VII—X represent respectively $M/20\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/10\text{-Am. Ac.}$, $M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/10\text{-Am. Ac.}$, $M/40\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/6\text{-Am. Ac.}$, and $M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/3\text{-Am. Ac.}$

In thermometric titration lead nitrate solution was taken in a Dewar flask kept within a second Dewar flask. A Beckman thermometer was placed to register temperature. Ammonium acetate solution was then added one c.c. at a time at regular intervals from a burette and changes in temperature were noted after each addition. Stirring, addition

of reagent and observations have been conducted under the conditions laid down by Dutoit (*loc. cit.*). The smooth nature of the curve is indicative of the success of such applications. The change of temperature after each addition has been plotted against respective volumes of ammonium acetate. Curves I and II (Fig. 1) represent the experimental data. The breaks in the curve indicate the proportion in which the complex formation takes place.

The conductivity measurements have been recorded both in equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions. Conductivity of the individual compounds and also of their mixtures have been measured. The data have been shown in the accompanying tables. The divergence from the additivity rule has been plotted in the curves.

Curve III (Fig. 2) shows conductometric titration results and curves IV-VI (Fig. 3) and curves VII-X (Fig. 4) demonstrate divergence from the additivity rule in equimolar and non-equimolar solutions respectively.

The conductivity apparatus was fitted with thermo-ionic valve amplifiers and so the experimental error in determining resistance was brought within 0.1%. The mean of three values of resistance was always taken. The thermostat was so adjusted that the temperature varied within 0.05°. For each series of measurements to begin with, the platinum electrode was deplatinised and recoated with black deposit of spongy platinum. In consideration of the precautions that have been taken in every step it is clear that the probable error due to all sources cannot exceed 0.2%.

In our investigation reciprocal of the observed resistance *i.e.*, conductance was sufficient to draw the curve. So the cell constant was not determined.

TABLE I

Conductivity experiment of $M/10\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $M/10\text{-CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (Curve IV, Fig. 3)

Temp. = 31.6°.

$M/10 \text{ Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.	Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (1) $\times 10^3 = C_1$	$M/10 \text{ Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.	Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (2) $\times 10^3 = C_2$	$C_1 + C_2 = C_3$	$M/10(\text{PbNO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.	$M/10 \text{ Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.	Condy. of (6) $\times 10^3 = C_4$	$C_3 - C_4$
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)			
100	0	75.16	0	..	0	75.16	100	0	75.16	0
95	5	72.15	5	95	2.54	74.69	95	5	72.89	1.80
90	10	68.87	10	90	4.96	73.83	90	10	69.93	3.90
85	15	65.79	15	85	7.25	73.04	85	15	67.52	5.52
80	20	63.08	20	80	9.66	72.74	80	20	65.62	7.12
75	25	59.91	25	75	11.92	71.83	75	25	62.96	8.87
70	30	56.37	30	70	14.12	70.49	70	30	60.46	10.03
65	35	53.25	35	65	16.29	69.54	65	35	57.74	11.80
60	40	49.79	40	60	18.59	68.38	60	40	55.30	13.08
55	45	46.86	45	55	20.75	67.61	55	45	53.07	14.54
50	50	43.29	50	50	22.91	66.20	50	50	49.98	16.22
45	55	39.62	55	45	24.83	64.45	45	55	48.40	16.05
40	60	36.37	60	40	26.86	63.23	40	60	47.30	15.93
35	65	32.08	65	35	28.92	60.98	35	65	45.80	15.18
30	70	28.75	70	30	30.91	59.38	30	70	44.82	14.54
25	75	24.23	75	25	33.06	57.29	25	75	44.01	13.28
20	80	19.98	80	20	35.14	55.12	20	80	43.29	11.83
15	85	15.53	85	15	37.30	52.83	15	85	42.76	10.09
10	90	10.86	90	10	39.93	49.97	10	90	42.60	7.37
5	95	5.74	95	5	40.93	46.67	5	95	42.46	4.21
—	—	—	100	0	42.76	—	—	100	42.76	0

TABLE II

Conductivity experiment of $M/20\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $M/20\text{-CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (Curve V, Fig. 3)
Temp. = 30°.

$M/20\text{ Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.		Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (1) $\times 10^3 = C_1$.	$M/20\text{ Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.		Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (3) $\times 10^3 = C_2$.	$C_1 + C_2 = C_3$.	$M/20\text{ Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.		$M/20\text{ Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.	Condy. of (6) $\times 10^3 = C_4$.	$C_3 - C_4$.
(1)	(2)			(3)	(4)				(5)	(6)			
100	0		40.60	0			0	40.60	100	0		40.60	0
95	5		38.80	5		95	1.40	40.20	95	5		39.30	0.90
90	10		37.14	10		90	2.67	39.71	90	10		38.17	1.54
85	15		35.42	15		85	3.71	39.13	85	15		36.68	2.45
80	20		33.72	20		80	4.91	38.83	80	20		35.37	3.26
75	25		32.02	25		75	6.02	38.04	75	25		33.88	4.16
70	30		30.40	30		70	7.09	37.49	70	30		31.54	5.38
65	35		28.57	35		65	8.15	36.72	65	35		31.03	5.69
60	40		26.75	40		60	9.15	36.06	60	40		29.83	6.45
55	45		25.00	45		55	10.27	35.37	55	45		28.37	6.98
50	50		23.07	50		50	11.35	34.42	50	50		26.95	7.47
45	55		21.08	55		45	12.41	33.49	45	55		26.10	7.39
40	60		18.90	60		40	13.50	32.40	40	60		25.16	7.24
35	65		16.96	65		35	14.47	31.43	35	65		24.30	7.13
30	70		14.88	70		30	15.48	30.34	30	70		23.68	6.66
25	75		12.57	75		25	16.46	29.03	25	75		22.83	6.20
20	80		10.30	80		20	17.65	27.95	20	80		22.46	5.49
15	85		7.99	85		15	18.68	26.67	15	85		22.18	4.49
10	90		5.52	90		10	19.68	25.18	10	90		21.75	3.43
5	95		2.92	95		5	20.68	23.60	5	95		21.51	2.09
—	—		—	100		0	21.65	21.65	0	100		21.65	0

TABLE III

Conductivity experiment of $M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $M/30\text{-CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (Curve VI, Fig. 3)
Temp. = 31.6°.

$M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.		Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (1) $\times 10^3 = C_1$.	$M/30\text{-Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.		Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (3) $\times 10^3 = C_2$.	$C_1 + C_2 = C_3$.	$M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.		$M/30\text{-Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.	Condy. of (6) $\times 10^3 = C_4$.	$C_3 - C_4$.
(1)	(2)			(3)	(4)				(5)	(6)			
100	0		30.32	0			0	30.32	100	0		30.32	0
95	5		29.36	5		95	0.92	30.28	95	5		29.51	0.77
90	10		27.96	10		90	1.77	29.73	90	10		28.30	1.43
85	15		26.53	15		85	2.60	29.13	85	15		27.06	2.07
80	20		25.30	20		80	3.39	28.69	80	20		26.10	2.59
75	25		23.84	25		75	4.23	28.07	75	25		24.93	3.14
70	30		22.49	30		70	5.02	27.51	70	30		23.84	3.67
65	35		21.22	35		65	5.85	27.07	65	35		23.00	4.07
60	40		19.78	40		60	6.65	26.43	60	40		21.83	4.60
55	45		18.32	45		55	7.44	25.76	55	45		20.88	4.88
50	50		16.82	50		50	8.24	25.06	50	50		19.78	5.28
45	55		15.34	55		45	9.05	24.39	45	55		19.18	5.21
40	60		13.28	60		40	9.78	23.04	40	60		18.46	5.18
35	65		12.27	65		35	10.49	22.76	35	65		17.72	5.04
30	70		10.76	70		30	11.30	22.06	30	70		17.32	4.74
25	75		9.14	75		25	12.02	21.16	25	75		16.68	4.48
20	80		7.48	80		20	12.75	20.23	20	80		16.45	3.78
15	85		5.73	85		15	13.49	19.17	15	85		16.16	3.01
10	90		3.94	90		10	14.19	18.13	10	90		15.96	2.17
5	95		1.00	95		5	14.97	17.07	5	95		15.77	1.30
..	..		0	100		0	15.84	15.84	0	100		15.84	0

TABLE IV

Conductivity experiment of $M/20\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $M/10\text{-CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (Curve VII, Fig. 4)

Temp. = 30°

$M/20\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.		Condy. of (1) $\times 10^3 = C_1$	$M/10\text{-Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.		Condy. of (3) $\times 10^3 = C_2$	$C_1 - C_2 = C_3$	$M/10\text{Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.		Condy. of (6) $\times 10^3 = C_4$	$C_3 - C_4$
(1)	Water added in c.c.		(3)	Water added in c.c.			(6)	(8)		
100	0	40.60	..	..	40.60	100	0	40.60	0	
95	5	38.80	..	..	41.32	95	5	39.34	1.98	
90	10	37.14	10	90	4.79	90	10	38.39	3.54	
85	15	35.52	15	85	7.05	85	15	37.30	5.27	
80	20	33.68	20	80	9.25	80	20	36.15	6.78	
75	25	31.98	25	75	11.44	75	25	35.57	7.83	
70	30	30.28	30	70	13.62	70	30	34.83	9.07	
65	35	28.53	35	65	15.65	65	35	34.28	9.90	
60	40	26.68	40	60	17.74	60	40	33.89	10.53	
56	44	25.34	44	56	19.40	56	44	33.50	11.24	
55	45	24.93	45	55	19.78	55	45	33.59	11.12	
50	50	22.99	50	50	21.78	50	50	33.82	10.95	
45	55	20.99	55	45	23.84	45	55	34.16	10.67	
40	60	18.80	60	40	25.74	40	60	34.34	10.20	
35	65	16.85	65	35	27.84	35	65	35.02	9.77	
30	70	14.77	70	30	29.87	30	70	35.66	8.98	
25	75	12.47	75	25	31.80	25	75	36.59	7.68	
20	80	10.30	80	20	33.77	20	80	37.49	6.58	
15	85	7.98	85	15	35.70	15	85	38.23	5.48	
10	90	5.52	90	10	37.77	10	90	39.22	4.07	
5	95	2.92	95	5	39.62	5	95	40.20	2.34	
..	..	..	100	0	41.60	..	100	41.60	0	

TABLE V

Conductivity experiment of $M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $M/10\text{-CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (Curve VIII, Fig. 4)

Temp. = 30°

$M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.		Condy. of (1) $\times 10^3 = C_1$	$M/10\text{-Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.		Condy. of (3) $\times 10^3 = C_2$	$C_1 + C_2 = C_3$	$M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.		Condy. of (6) $\times 10^3 = C_4$	$C_3 - C_4$
(1)	Water added in c.c.		(3)	Water added in c.c.			(6)	(8)		
100	0	29.11	..	..	29.11	100	0	29.11	0	
95	5	27.97	..	..	2.52	95	5	28.41	2.08	
90	10	26.64	10	90	4.79	90	10	27.95	3.68	
85	15	25.68	15	85	7.11	85	15	27.28	5.51	
80	20	24.13	20	80	9.36	80	20	26.99	6.50	
75	25	22.80	25	75	11.50	75	25	27.10	7.20	
70	30	21.57	30	70	13.69	70	30	27.17	8.09	
65	35	20.14	35	65	15.71	65	35	27.43	8.42	
60	40	18.78	40	60	17.03	60	40	28.07	8.64	
58	42	18.33	42	58	18.71	58	42	28.30	8.74	
55	45	17.50	45	55	19.87	55	45	28.76	8.61	
50	50	16.09	50	50	21.93	50	50	29.55	8.47	
45	55	14.64	55	45	23.94	45	55	30.52	8.06	
40	60	13.19	60	40	25.99	40	60	31.60	7.58	
35	65	11.78	65	35	27.95	35	65	32.64	7.09	
30	70	10.24	70	30	29.99	30	70	33.72	6.51	
25	75	8.60	75	25	31.98	25	75	35.04	5.63	
20	80	7.12	80	20	33.87	20	80	36.24	4.75	
15	85	5.47	85	15	35.96	15	85	37.59	3.84	
10	90	3.76	90	10	37.87	10	90	38.80	2.83	
5	95	2.00	95	5	39.62	5	95	40.27	1.35	
..	..	..	100	..	41.67	..	100	41.67	0	

TABLE VI

Conductivity experiment of $M/40\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $M/6\text{-CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (Curve IX, Fig. 4)
Temp. = 30°

(1)		(2)	(3)		(4)	(5)	(6)		(7)	(8)
$M/40\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.	Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (1) $\times 10^3 = C_1$	$M/6\text{-Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.	Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (3) $\times 10^3 = C_2$	$C_1 + C_2 = C_3$	$M/40\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.	$M/6\text{-Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.	Condy. of (6) $\times 10^3 = C_4$	$C_3 - C_4$
100	..	23.35	..	..	..	23.35	100	..	22.35	0
95	5	22.36	5	95	4.25	26.61	95	5	23.12	3.49
90	10	21.40	10	90	7.99	29.39	90	10	24.74	5.65
85	15	20.38	15	85	11.74	32.12	85	15	24.73	7.39
80	20	19.34	20	80	15.46	34.80	80	20	26.44	8.31
75	25	18.33	25	75	19.03	37.36	75	25	28.41	8.95
70	30	17.23	30	70	22.57	39.80	70	30	30.64	9.16
65	35	16.09	35	65	26.10	42.19	65	35	32.67	9.52
64	36	15.90	36	64	26.77	42.67	64	36	33.04	9.63
60	40	15.07	40	60	29.45	44.52	60	40	35.01	9.45
55	45	14.05	45	55	32.78	46.83	55	45	37.75	9.08
50	50	12.83	50	50	36.10	48.93	50	50	40.27	8.66
45	55	11.70	55	45	39.45	51.15	45	55	42.78	8.37
40	60	10.58	60	40	42.60	53.18	40	60	45.43	7.75
35	65	9.40	65	35	45.85	55.28	35	65	47.96	7.29
30	70	8.14	70	30	48.81	56.95	30	70	50.52	6.43
25	75	6.90	75	25	51.96	58.80	25	75	53.16	5.64
20	80	5.62	80	20	55.33	60.95	20	80	55.30	4.65
15	85	4.33	85	15	58.25	62.58	15	85	58.99	3.59
10	90	2.96	90	10	61.89	64.54	10	90	61.89	2.70
5	95	1.57	95	5	63.89	65.64	5	95	64.44	1.02
..	..	..	100	..	66.82	66.82	..	100	66.82	0

TABLE VII

Conductivity experiment of $M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $M/3\text{-CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (Curve X, Fig. 4)
Temp. = 30°

(1)		(2)	(3)		(4)	(5)	(6)		(7)	(8)
$M/30\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.	Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (1) $\times 10^3 = C_1$	$M/3\text{-Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.	Water added in c.c.	Condy. of (3) $\times 10^3 = C_2$	$C_1 + C_2 = C_3$	$M/3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. in c.c.	$M/3\text{-Am. Ac.}$ soln. in c.c.	Condy. of (6) $\times 10^3 = C_4$	$C_3 - C_4$
100	..	29.23	..	..	..	29.23	100	..	29.23	0
95	5	28.07	5	95	8.02	36.09	95	5	29.99	6.10
90	10	26.95	10	90	15.25	42.20	90	10	32.51	9.69
85	15	25.78	15	85	22.19	47.97	85	15	36.15	11.82
80	20	24.31	20	80	28.76	53.07	80	20	40.42	12.65
75	25	22.90	25	75	35.29	58.19	75	25	45.05	13.14
70	30	21.66	30	70	41.73	63.39	70	30	49.83	13.56
69	31	21.40	31	69	43.29	64.69	69	31	51.02	13.67
65	35	20.22	35	65	47.91	68.13	65	35	54.61	13.52
60	40	18.86	40	60	54.24	73.01	60	40	59.91	13.10
55	45	17.60	45	55	60.24	77.84	55	45	65.28	12.56
50	50	16.25	50	50	65.54	87.89	50	50	70.13	11.66
45	55	14.70	55	45	72.03	86.73	45	55	75.82	10.91
40	60	13.27	60	40	77.94	91.21	40	60	80.86	10.35
35	65	11.87	65	35	83.26	95.13	35	65	85.99	9.14
30	70	10.37	70	30	88.91	99.28	30	70	90.91	8.37
25	75	8.76	75	25	94.20	102.96	25	75	95.52	7.44
20	80	7.14	80	20	98.98	106.10	20	80	99.80	6.30
15	85	5.54	85	15	104.90	110.44	15	85	105.50	4.94
10	90	3.79	90	10	110.30	114.09	10	90	110.30	3.79
5	95	2.02	95	5	115.50	117.52	5	95	115.10	2.42
..	..	..	100	..	119.60	119.60	..	100	119.60	0

Calculation of the Value of the Dissociation Constant K .

The general equation relating the value of the dissociation constant K as derived by Job is as follows :—

$$\frac{c^{m+n+1} \times p^{n-1} [(pm+n)x-n]^{m+n}}{m^{n-1} \cdot n^{m-1} \cdot (p-1)^{m+n-1} \times [n-(m+n)x]} \quad \dots (i)$$

where m represents mols of one of the components say A

n represents mols of the other component say B

c , the molar concentration of A

pc B

x c.c. of B combining with $(1-x)$ c.c. of A to give the maximum changing effect.

Putting $p=1$ in equation (i) i.e., in the case of equimolecular solutions we have

$$m, n = \frac{1-x}{x} \quad \dots (ii)$$

With reference to thermometric curves I and II (Fig. 1), conductometric titration curve III (Fig. 2) and conductometric measurement curves IV, V and VI (Fig. 3) showing divergence from the additivity rule due to complex formation in equimolecular mixtures, it is evident that one mole of lead nitrate reacts with one mole of ammonium acetate i.e., $1-x/x=1$ So m and n in equation (ii) have identical values i.e., $m=n=1$; putting this value of m and n in the general equation (i) we get the following

$$K = \frac{\{c(p+1)x-1\}^2}{(p-1)(1-2x)} \quad \dots (iii)$$

whence the following values of K has been calculated.

From molar concentrations the values of c and p have been worked out by knowing the values of α , the degree of dissociation of the two salts in the dilutions concerned. Results are tabulated below.

TABLE VIII

Table No.	Fig. No.	Curve No.	c	p	x	$k \times 10^3$	Mean $k \times 10^3$
4	4	VII	0.03718	2.206	0.44	43.18	40.76
5	4	VIII	0.02635	3.112	0.42	41.21	
6	4	IX	0.02035	6.600	0.36	39.10	
7	4	X	0.02635	9.232	0.31	39.77	

DISCUSSION

In reviewing the works of the previous investigations it has been clearly pointed out that no direct or definite evidence as regards the existence of acetato complex of lead was arrived at. The indirect evidence based upon the measurements of solubility was the only source of information. The solubility determination in such cases also meets with adverse circumstances. Even the most recent investigation of Edmonds and Birnbaum is based upon the assumptions that

(i) Wieland's higher lead-acetato perchlorates do not exist in solution to any appreciable extent. (ii) No acetato-plumbite ion is formed. (iii) Probability of hydrolysis and basic salt formation is negligible. (iv) The effect of IO_3^- ion liberated in the reaction

in depressing the solubility has been counterbalanced by the formation of an anionic complex which increases the solubility. (v) Neither lead perchlorato-iodate nor lead perchlorate is formed in solution.

In our investigation, however, direct and definite evidence as regards the formation of a lead-acetato $[\text{PbC}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2]^-$ cation has been put forward. The two physicochemical measurements, namely (a) conductivity and (b) thermal effect, we adopted, are independent of each other as regards principle. The former depends on colligative property and the latter serves as an index to chemical reaction only. Combining these two methods we have been able to study the reaction within wide range of concentrations. The nature of the curves shows it definitely that one and only one compound is formed in all dilutions. The constant value of the dissociation constant in varying concentrations proves it definitely that the only complex formed in solution is the lead-acetato cation $[\text{PbC}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2]^+$. Though the lead-acetato nitrate has not yet been isolated yet the isolation of the compounds like

like $\left\langle \begin{matrix} n \\ \text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2 \end{matrix} \right.$ where n stands for Cl, Br, I or ClO, proves the existence of such complex compound in solid state as well. The mean value of the dissociation constant deduced from our measurements is 40.76×10^{-3} at 30° , whereas the dissociation constant from the solubility measurement of Edmonds and Birnbaum is 9.65×10^{-3} at 25° and such a divergence cannot be attributed to difference in temperature alone. It may be rather due to the disturbing effects already pointed out in the determination of solubility in such cases under such conditions.

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